

ISic4424

Boundary stone (?)

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

terminus

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-06-30 - Jonathan Prag edited the file from published data

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Gualtherus provides the only record of this text, described as recorded by one 'Fran. Bella', 'in agro Catanensi'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, lost

Physical Description

The object is not described in the surviving transcriptions

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

By analogy with other known texts, the text may have been divided over two lines; a line is marked above the first three letters in the edition of Gualtherus

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No description of the text is preserved

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. EK(vac.unknown)L(vac.unknown)KAT

Apparatus

Text after Gualtherus

Translation**Commentary**

The only record of this text is that of Gualtherus 1624, reporting a text noted by one 'Fran. Bella'. The form of the text, including the line above the first two letters, is very similar to the second and third lines of ISic1404 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1404>] , preserved in Adrano museum, and from the right bank of the Simeto river (see that text for further commentary).

The spacing in the text of Gualtherus, and the presence of the line above the first two letters, encourages the idea that the text was on a boundary stone, in large letters, divided over two or three lines, as in the case of the Adrano stone (whether the 'L' was on a separate line or not, in this example, can only be guessed). A second, very similar text (ISic1338 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1338>]) was recorded by Gualtherus, and both are repeated in CIG and IG. Manganaro (1994) briefly discusses these texts, and argues that they should be considered distinct from the set of texts preserved in the manuscript collection of Gaetano Marini, from Sferri, in the territory of Paterno, and reproduced by several scholars, including Ferrua 1989 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/759ZXHKQ>] , p. 123-124 nr. 471 (ISic4425 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4425>] , ISic4426 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4426>] , ISic4427 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4427>]); the second and third of those texts are similar to this one, but seemingly not identical. The only text actually preserved is that in Adrano museum.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492946

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Bibliography

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